

Exploring Research Integrity Indicators: Response from project sponsors and UK Committee on Research Integrity

The starting point for most discussions about integrity in research is around numbers of cases of misconduct, and yet we know that this doesn't tell us enough about the overall quality and progress of UK research. This gap between what we currently measure and what we need to know led Cancer Research UK (CRUK), GuildHE and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) to commission Research Consulting to explore what indicators of research integrity exist, or could be proposed, that are valid, reliable, ethical, and practical. For this work indicators are defined as factors, either quantitative or qualitative, that allow us to check, assess or measure progress and achievement¹.

The project built on the UK Concordat to Support Research Integrity² and successfully fostered discussions about how to build a co-created set of indicators for research integrity. We thank everyone involved for their insight and contribution. Whilst the project highlighted the range of nuances, complexities and potential challenges involved, we were encouraged by the strong interest and enthusiasm for continuing the debate. Here, we, the project sponsors and the new UK Committee on Research Integrity (UK CORI)³, identify a set of five working principles to inform the future development of indicators and invite the sector to join us in taking forward this important work.

Five working principles for developing indicators of research integrity

Be co-created

- Research takes place in many different environments and disciplines, which leads to different priorities when it comes to maintaining or tackling issues around research integrity. This work confirmed little interest in creating a single standard on research integrity for the sector, suggesting that disciplinary differences may necessitate a series of discipline-specific standards. To ensure that the heterogeneity of the sector is considered when developing indicators, co-creation and co-ownership across the breadth of the sector is essential and should include an array of stakeholders from a broad disciplinary and organisational spread.

Have a formative purpose

- Connecting indicators to the issues that need solving, and the outcomes for research integrity we want to achieve, is integral to their success. Indicators should have a formative focus and should not be created for their own sake; they should support a research system that enables researchers to grow and improve.

Be framed in a positive way

- Indicators should be designed to facilitate and promote good research practice and behaviours rather than be punitive or compliance driven. They should not be driven by measurement or metrics, but rather enable opportunities for learning and development that can be embedded so that those working in research are better supported to conduct it with the highest integrity.

Be developed at a macro level

- Indicators would be most useful to drive sector-level change by encouraging good research practice and behaviours, supporting continuous improvement, and reducing problem trends. It is vital to steer away from unnecessary bureaucracy and to consider organisational and individual pressures in what is already a highly pressured and time poor research environment.

¹ <https://www.oecd.org/dac/peer-reviews/Development-Results-Note.pdf>

² <https://www.universitiesuk.ac.uk/topics/research-and-innovation/concordat-support-research-integrity>

³ <https://www.ukri.org/what-we-offer/supporting-healthy-research-and-innovation-culture/research-integrity/uk-committee-on-research-integrity>

Drive improvements in research culture

- Artificially separating research integrity from interlinked topics such as research culture, or equality, diversity and inclusion, could pose problems in the longer term. However, considering both at the same time may lead to conversations which are too broad and as a result inhibit meaningful progress. Finding the balance, while avoiding duplication and fostering connectivity with other initiatives, is integral to success.

What next

We will use the working principles to raise awareness of this project and explore potential commonality between disciplines and research environments. The findings and future discussion will feed into mapping how indicators may apply in different contexts, bearing in mind distinctions in reach and significance, and into ongoing work on research assessment⁴. Building on the first principle, we will use a set of discussion prompts to hear views from across the research workforce. However, to genuinely move this discussion forward we encourage everyone to use this initial exploratory work to discuss what research integrity looks like in their specific context and what indicators might be useful to foster integrity.

Workshops taking place across the UK will continue the dialogue, focusing on how individuals can work together, co-designing potential indicators to ensure they are applicable across the full diversity of institutions and research environments. Through the committee, we will then seek to develop a cross-sector mechanism, involving different parts of the research environment, to consider reflections from these workshops. They will determine if further work needs to be commissioned to give the research sector and public greater confidence in the integrity of UK research and efforts being made to maintain, recognise and promote UK research and those working on it.

Opportunities for the sector, prompts for further discussion

Using the principles, we invite the sector to reflect on how we might take forward this work together.

- What does your organisation believe is the most important opportunity indicators might provide?
- What information on research integrity does your organisation or discipline use?
- What additional information could be gathered that might be useful for indicating progress on an institutional, departmental, or individual basis on research integrity?
- How would you balance the tensions in the working principles when developing indicators for research integrity?
- Which facets⁵ are the most feasible, which are the most important and are there others that should be considered?

Please send your thoughts to secretariat@ukcori.org.

⁴ Such as <https://www.ukri.org/about-us/research-england/research-excellence/future-research-assessment-programme-frap/#contents-list>

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6827947> figure 1